

STUDIES ON KING OYSTER MUSHROOM (*Pleurotus eryngii*) CULTIVATION ON DIFFERENT SUBSTRATES

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Abstract

The study was conducted at the All India Coordinated Research Project on Mushroom, College of Agriculture, Pune to find suitable substrate for cultivation of king oyster mushroom. Seven different agricultural wastes viz. sawdust, wheat straw, soybean straw, sugarcane bagasse, sugarcane trash, paddy straw and spent mushroom substrate were evaluated to find the growth and yield of king oyster mushroom. The experiment was carried out using completely randomized design with seven treatments and three replications. Results revealed that the spawn run period and the days to pinhead formation were faster in soybean straw (16.24 and 11.44 days, respectively), this was followed by paddy straw (17.40 and 13.59 days, respectively) while spent mushroom substrate recorded the longest (39.91 and 22.29 days, respectively). Stipe length ranged from 5.84 cm in spent mushroom substrate to 7.82 cm in sawdust while the pileus diameter was between 4.99 cm in spent mushroom substrate and 6.72 cm in soybean straw. The maximum biological yield was obtained with soybean straw (726.46 g) followed by paddy straw (717.56 g) whereas lowest yield was recorded in spent mushroom substrate (312.55 g) per kg dry substrate. The soybean straw can be used as the best substrate for king oyster mushroom cultivation as it performed the best in respect of all fruit body, growth and yield attributing characters of king oyster mushroom with highest yields.

Key words: King oyster mushroom, substrates and yield.

Introduction

In the 21st century, addressing the challenges of increasing population, declining arable land, urbanization, industrialization, and climate change requires a focus on secondary agriculture and novel crops like mushroom cultivation, which promotes sustainability and bioconversion of agricultural, industrial, and household waste.

Edible mushroom cultivation is a significant commercial agricultural sector globally that offers a protein-rich diet while reducing environmental pollution. (Sanchez, 2010; Zhang *et al.*, 2016). India has seen an increase in mushroom type and productivity, with *Agaricus bisporus* being the most farmed mushroom globally and *Pleurotus* spp. accounting for 27% of all cultivated mushrooms. (Atila, 2017).

Oyster mushroom belongs to the phylum Basidiomycota, Class Agaricomycetes, Order Agaricales, and Family Pleurotaceae. *Pleurotus eryngii* is the largest species in the *Pleurotus* genus. Young specimens have a thick, white, meaty stem and a huge tan cap.

Pleurotus, a macro fungus with a distinct fruiting body, is a unique biota that collects food by secreting degradative enzymes. In tropical and subtropical climates, oyster mushrooms (also known as Dhingri) are easy to grow. *Pleurotus* species are distinguished by the quickness with which their mycelial growth occurs. Composting substrate is not required for the creation of oyster mushrooms. Oyster mushrooms may be dried simply for a longer shelf life for export. (Maheswari *et al.*, 2020).

The cap of *Pleurotus eryngii* is medium-sized and brown-brownish red in colour. At the beginning, it has a round shape that flattens out and finally turns into a tube shape. The stem is situated centrally or excentrally. The gills are white and run down deep on the stem, which is also white. The caps upper skin is thicker than the other oyster mushroom strain, so it won't get flaky if the relative humidity is lower in the growing room. The advantage of this strain as compared to other *Pleurotus* strain is that at storage (+2 °C) *Pleurotus eryngii* keep its shelf life and marketable quality for a long time (upto 12 days) and also does not get affected by the transport. (Gyorfi and Hajdu, 2007).

Among 14 species tested in a search for natural estrogen-like materials from mushrooms, *P. eryngii* extract demonstrated the strongest estrogen-like action. The findings show that the ethanolic extract of *P.eryngii* protects against bone loss caused by estrogen deprivation without having a major impact on the uterus. (Shimizu *et al.*, 2006)

Pleurotus eryngii may include immune-boosting compounds. Including *Pleurotus eryngii* in your diet, may act as a cholesterol-lowering agent.

The research that has revealed numerous chemicals originating from *P. eryngii* have led to the widespread view that this fungus has antihypertensive, immunomodulatory, anticancer, antibacterial, antioxidant, antihypercholesterolemic, antihyperglycemic, antiviral, antifungal, antiinflammatory, and antiosteoporotic properties (Wasser and Weis,1999).

Pleurotus eryngii mushroom cultivation has proven effective on a variety of agricultural and agro-industrial wastes such as sawdust, wheat straw, millet straw, soybean straw, cotton waste, peanut shells, sugarcane bagasse, wheat and rice bran. (Cangy and Peerally, 1995; Torng *et al.*, 2000; Zervakis *et al.*, 2001; Ohga and Royse, 2004; and Kirbag and Akyuz, 2008).

Material And Methods**Study Location**

The research work was accomplished at the All India Coordinated Research Project on Mushroom, College of Agriculture, Pune (MS).

Mother culture

Pure culture of *Pleurotus eryngii* was cultured on malt extract agar (MEA) medium and incubated at 20 ± 1 °C. Malt extract agar (MEA) slants were prepared and the culture of *Pleurotus eryngii* was inoculated on these slants aseptically under laminar air flow. The inoculated slants were incubated at 20±1°C until the fungal mycelium on the agar slants had completely grown.

Preparation of master spawn

For preparing the master spawn, wheat grains were used as substrate. The wheat grains were cleaned and soaked in water overnight and were boiled in the water for 25-30 min. After drying, these seeds were mixed with 4 % calcium carbonate on wet grain weight basis. Properly mixed grains are then filled in 3/4 capacity in conical flasks or polypropylene bags (500 gm) and these were sterilized in an autoclave at 20 lbs for one and half hour. After cooling, these flask and bags were inoculated with *Pleurotus eryngii* culture in a sterile (UV sterilized) laminar flow chamber. The flasks were incubated at 20 ±1°C in an incubator. The spawn thus prepared was used for preparation of commercial spawn.

Preparation of commercial spawn

The mother spawn was inoculated into sterilized polypropylene bags containing autoclaved wheat grains under laminar air flow. Under aseptic conditions, 4-6 spatula full of mother spawn was inoculated in each polypropylene bag consisting of 500 g of wet sterilized wheat grains. The bags were re-plugged and the contents were gently shaken to disseminate the inoculum evenly across the substrate. These bags

were then incubated for 7-10 days at 20±1°C in an incubator. After fully impregnating the commercial spawn substrate with mycelium, the spawn was ready for use.

Substrate preparation and sterilization

King Oyster mushroom was grown on various substrates viz. sawdust, wheat straw, soybean straw, paddy straw, sugarcane bagasse, sugarcane trash, etc. The experiment was laid out by using these chopped straws (3-5 cm) of wheat, paddy, sugarcane trash. These straws were placed in gunny bags and immersed in a fresh water solution with the proper concentrations of formalin and Bavistin chemicals i. e. Bavistin 7.5 g + formaldehyde 150 ml /100 L of water for 16-18 hours. After soaking, the surplus water was permitted to drain out.

Bed filling and spawning

The spawning was carried out in pre-sprayed room (48 h with 2% formaldehyde). The sterilized substrate got ready for filling and spawning in polybags when the substrate moisture content remains about 65%. Sterilized straw was layer spawned in high density polythene bags of size 45x 30 cm (100 gauge) by using freshly prepared pure wheat grain spawn @ 4 % on wet weight basis. The bags were filled with wet substrate @ 2kg/bag (1 kg dry straw). After spawning, the polythene bag's top was tied with thread and had 20- 25 pinholes perforation all over for ventilation of substrate. Few pinholes were also made at bottom of the bag for drainage.

Incubation and spawn run

After bed filling, the beds were kept on iron racks in the incubation room. Required ventilation, proper light, optimum temperature (i.e., 25-28 °C) and relative humidity (i.e., 70 to 85%) were maintained in this room till completion of mycelial run. After 20-30 days of spawning, when spawn run gets completed and bags turns white in colour due to white mycelial growth, were used for casing.

Casing Casing material: Coir pith + FYM (4:1, v/v) both two years old (pH adjusted to the 7.2 to 7.5 with CaCO₃). The casing material was water leached for 8 hrs before sterilization. It was sterilized by using Bavistin (0.1%) and formaldehyde (4%). The bags were opened and folded outwards. The 3-5 cm thick pre-sterilized casing layer was made on the top of the bed.

Cropping and Harvesting

All of the necessary environmental conditions for primordial development and fruit body development were met. Ventilation of 2 -3 hours per day was provided to maintain CO₂ levels in the growing rooms. Room temperature and humidity were maintained between 17-20°C and 65 85 % respectively for formation of fruiting body during fructification. Until the completion of the cropping season, the beds were regularly watered once a day. Mushroom were harvested when the mushroom cap surface were flat to slightly up-rolled at the cap margins. Harvesting of fully mature mushrooms was done by twisting them slightly and carefully so that the young developing pinheads in the vicinity of the mature sporophores did not become vulnerable to any sort of damage and loss. Mushrooms were harvested, trimmed off at the

substrate level, counted and weighed separately for each replication at every harvest. Yield was recorded and the biological efficiency was also calculated.

Biological efficiency (%)

The biological efficiency was calculated by the following formula,

$$\text{Biological efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Fresh weight of mushrooms}}{\text{Dry weight of substrate}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

The data collected for various observations was analyzed using CRD. The standard statistical methods as described by Panse and Sukhmate (1985) and an online OPSTAT application were followed for statistical significance.

Result And Discussion

During the present investigation on the “Studies on King Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus eryngii*) cultivation on different substrates”, the results obtained are discussed as below.

Fruit body observations of king oyster mushroom

Colour

The caps colour of king oyster mushrooms vary from pale brown to dark brown, while the stems are creamy white.

Odour

King oyster mushrooms are famous for their rich umami flavor, which is sometimes compared to the flavor of seafood or scallops. When cooked, they have a deep, meaty aroma that enhances a variety of cuisines.

Stipe length

The stipe length of the king oyster mushroom was measured in all treatments. The length of the stipe ranged from 5.84 to 7.82 cm. The stipe length (7.82 cm) on sawdust substrate was found to be significantly superior to other treatments. The shortest stipe length (5.84 cm) was measured on the spent mushroom substrate (Table1).

The findings are consistent with those of Moonmoon *et al.* (2010), who found that the average stipe length of *Pleurotus eryngii* varied between 6.63 to 8.00 cm on sawdust substrate.

Stipe size

The results obtained for stipe size of king oyster mushroom are statistically non significant. However, the stipe size of king oyster mushroom varied from 5.06 to 7.17 cm. The maximum stipe size was recorded on soybean straw (7.17 cm), while the smallest stipe size (5.06 cm) was measured on spent mushroom substrate. (Table 1).

Pileus diameter

The data (Table 1) revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw had the largest pileus diameter (6.72 cm), followed by the treatment T4 paddy straw (6.63 cm), and the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate (4.99 cm) had the smallest pileus diameter.

The findings correspond with those of Moonmoon *et al.* (2010), who found that the pileus diameter of *Pleurotus eryngii* ranged from 5.25 to 6.83 cm.

Table: 1 Morphological characters of king oyster mushroom on different substrates

Sr. No.	Treatments	Stipe length (cm)	Pileus Diameter (cm)	Stipe size (cm)
1	T1- Sawdust	7.82	6.46	5.58
2	T2- Wheat straw	7.22	6.34	5.33
3	T3- Soybean straw	7.72	6.72	7.1
4	T4- Paddy straw	7.48	6.63	6.78
5	T5-Sugarcane bagasse	6.50	5.95	5.11
6	T6- Sugarcane trash	6.22	5.90	5.09
7	T7- Spent mushroom substrate	5.84	4.99	5.06
	SE±	0.48	0.44	0.19
	CD (0.05)	N.S.	N.S.	0.59

Growth performance

The observations, such as the days required for spawn run, pinhead development, and first, second, and third harvest were recorded.

Days required for spawn run

During incubation, observations on spawn run were recorded. The spawn run findings were statistically significant. The period required for spawn run ranged from 16.24 to 39.91 days (Table 2, Plate 1).

Among all treatments, treatment T3 soybean straw required the shortest incubation period of 16.24 days. The treatments T4 paddy straw and T2 wheat straw took 17.40 and 19.15 days, respectively, to complete the spawn run, while the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate took the longest (39.91 days) time for spawn run.

The observed results are consistent with those of Deora *et al.* (2021), who stated that the spawn run in paddy straw inoculated with *Pleurotus eryngii* was completed in 18.4 days after spawning and 19 days on wheat straw, respectively.

According to Hossain (2017), the period required to complete a spawn run in *Pleurotus sajor-caju* on sugarcane bagasse was 17 days, followed by 26 days on sugarcane leaves. Sawant *et al.* (2022) showed that a spawn run in soybean straw inoculated with *Pleurotus sajor-caju* took 17–19 days after spawning, while a sugarcane trash spawn run took 19–21 days for completion of spawn run.

Table: 2 Effect of different substrates on days required for spawn run and pinhead formation of king oyster mushroom

Sr. No.	Treatments	Days required for spawn run	Days required for pinhead formation
1	T1- Sawdust	25.79	17.69
2	T2- Wheat straw	19.15	14.81
3	T3- Soybean straw	16.24	11.44
4	T4- Paddy straw	17.40	13.59
5	T5-Sugarcane bagasse	19.64	16.00
6	T6- Sugarcane trash	24.89	18.40
7	T7- Spent mushroom substrate	39.91	22.29
	SE±	0.63	0.75
	CD (0.05)	1.93	2.29

Days required for pinhead formation

When the mushroom beds were transferred to the growing room and small pinheads began to emerge from the beds, the observations on pinhead formation were recorded. The data on days required for pinhead formation (Table 2, Fig. 2) revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw took the fewest days (11.44) for pinhead formation, which was found to be on par with the treatment T4 paddy straw (13.59 days), while the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate took the longest (22.29) days for pinhead formation.

The days required for pinhead emergence were recorded after the spawn run. It ranged from 11.44 to 22.29 days. The treatment T3 soybean straw resulted in early pinhead production after the spawn run. Deora *et al.* (2021) stated that the time required for pinhead formation in *Pleurotus eryngii* varied from 12.4 to 28 days after spawning, and Kirbag and Akyuz (2008) reported that 26.2 days were required for the appearance of pinheads in *Pleurotus eryngii* grown on wheat str

T1

T2

T3

T4

T5

T6

T7

T1- Sawdust T2- Wheat straw T3- Soybean straw
T4- Paddy straw T5- Sugarcane bagasse
T6- Sugarcane trash T7- Spent mushroom substrate

Plate 1: Effect of different substrates on spawn run in king oyster mushroom

Days required for harvesting:

After pinhead development, harvesting was carried out three times. The number of days needed for the first, second, and third harvest, were recorded (Table 3).

Table: 3 Effect of different substrates for days required for harvest of king oyster

Sr. No.	Treatments	mushroom		
		1 st harvest	2 nd harvest	3 rd harvest
1	T1- Sawdust	9.09	17.73	27.62
2	T2- Wheat straw	7.51	17.69	26.37
3	T3- Soybean straw	6.14	15.65	23.79
4	T4- Paddy straw	7.34	17.56	25.30
5	T5-Sugarcane bagasse	8.57	17.98	28.63
6	T6- Sugarcane trash	9.31	18.24	31.21
7	T7- Spent mushroom substrate	11.01	20.37	0.00
	SE±	0.65	0.76	0.96
	CD (0.05)	1.99	2.33	2.91

First harvest

The data in Table 3 revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw took the fewest days for first harvest (6.14 days), which was found to be at par with treatments T4 paddy straw (7.34 days), T2 wheat straw (7.51 days), and T5 sugarcane bagasse (8.57 days). Whereas the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate required the longest days (11.01 days) for the first harvest.

Second harvest

In the case of days required for the second harvest, the treatment T3 soybean straw took the minimum number of days for the second harvest (15.65 days), which was found to be at par with treatment T4 paddy straw (17.56 days), T2 wheat straw (17.69 days) and T1 sawdust substrate (17.73 days). While the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate took the maximum number of days (20.37 days) for the second harvest.

Third harvest

The data in Table 3 revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw required the fewest days for the third harvest (23.79 days), which was comparable to the treatments T4 rice straw (25.30 days), for the third harvest, while the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate failed to harvest.

The treatment T3 soybean straw required the fewest days for the first, second, and third harvests after pinhead formation, followed by

Table: 4 Effect of different substrates on number of fruiting bodies and average fruit body weight (g) of king oyster mushroom

Sr. No.	Treatments	Average fruit body weight (g)	No. of fruits per kg dry substrate
1	T1- Sawdust	28.65	23.52
2	T2- Wheat straw	28.71	24.25
3	T3- Soybean straw	29.26	24.87
4	T4- Paddy straw	30.18	24.07
5	T5-Sugarcane bagasse	26.87	21.85
6	T6- Sugarcane trash	24.80	18.58
7	T7- Spent mushroom substrate	21.35	14.65
	SE±	0.24	0.73
	CD (0.05)	2.89	2.22

The results are in line with those of Deora *et al.* (2021), who found that *Pleurotus eryngii* had an average fruit body weight ranging from 25.3 to 96.4 g. According to Khade *et al.* (2019), the average fruit body weight of *Hypsizygus ulmarius* ranged from 2.72 to 10.64 g.

Number of fruits per kg dry substrate

The number of fruits per bed was recorded at the time of each harvest (Table 4 and Fig. 2)

The data revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw produced considerably more fruiting bodies per bed (24.87) than treatment T2 wheat straw (24.25) and treatment T4 paddy straw (24.07). The treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate produced the lowest number of fruiting bodies, (14.65) fruits per bed. The number of fruiting bodies

treatment T2 wheat straw and treatment T4 paddy straw, whereas treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate required the maximum days (Table 3).

The findings are consistent with those of Ohga (2000), Akyüz and Yildiz (2007), Ohga and Royse (2004), and Obatake *et al.* (2003), who indicated that the days required for harvesting in *P. eryngii* ranged between 50 and 70 days. According to Mshandete and Kivaisi (2013), Hassan *et al.* (2010), Muhammad *et al.* (2005), and Shah *et al.* (2004), the time necessary for the first, second, and third harvests of oyster mushrooms ranged from 4 to 10 days, 15 to 28 days, and 32 to 52 days, respectively.

Yield parameters**Average fruit weight**

The average fruit body weight (g) was determined by randomly selecting 10 mature fruiting bodies from each treatment and the results were presented in the Table 4 and Fig 2.

The average body weight (g) of the fruits ranged from 21.35 to 30.18 g. The treatment T4 paddy straw had the highest average fruit body weight (30.18 g), followed by treatment T3 soybean straw (29.26 g) and treatment T2 wheat straw (28.71 g), while the treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate had the least average fruit body weight (21.35 g).

per bed varied from 14.65 to 24.87, in different treatments. The treatment T3 soybean straw was found to be superior to all other treatments.

The findings support those of Deora *et al.* (2021), who reported that *Pleurotus eryngii* produced 9.4 to 32.8 fruit bodies per bed. The data obtained correspond with Khade's (2019) findings that *Hypsizygus ulmarius* generated 6.11 to 89.56 fruit bodies per bed.

Yield

The yield performance of different treatments was recorded independently at the first, second, and third harvests, and the total yield (g) per kg dry substrate was determined (Table 5 and Fig 2).

The treatment T3 soybean straw produced the highest yield (726.46 g/kg dry substrate), followed by T4 paddy straw (717.56 g/kg dry substrate), T2 wheat straw (696.61 g/kg dry substrate), and T1 sawdust substrate (675.79 g/kg dry substrate). The treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate produced the lowest yield (312.55 g/kg dry substrate).

The findings correspond with those of Deora *et al.* (2021), who also reported that the yield of *P. eryngii* on wheat straw and rice straw was 767.4 g/kg and 884.0 g/kg dry substrate, respectively. Dhobale *et al.* (2023) determined the yield of *P. sajor-caju* on wheat straw to be 706.82 g/kg to 1306.82 g/kg dry straw. Sawant *et al.* (2022) measured the yield performance of *P. sajor-caju* on soybean straw, wheat straw, and sugarcane trash and found that it generated 752.64 g/kg, 654.01 g/kg, and 635.14 g/kg of dry substrate, respectively.

According to Khade *et al.* (2019), the total yield obtained by *Hypsizygus ulmarius* on wheat straw ranged from 320 g/kg to 831.11 g/kg dry substrate.

Patil *et al.* (2010) studied the yield performance of *Pleurotus* spp. on wheat straw and revealed that the mushroom yield was 720.66 g/kg dry substrate.

Biological efficiency (%)

The influence of different treatments on biological efficiency of king oyster mushroom was determined by using the formulae given by Chang and Miles (1989), and the results are shown in Table 5 and Fig.2.

The data revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw showed significantly higher biological efficiency (72.64%) than the other treatments, which was found to be at par with treatment T4 paddy straw (71.75%). The treatment T7 spent mushroom substrate showed the lowest biological efficiency (31.25%).

Table: 5 Effect of different substrates on yield (g/ kg dry substrate) and biological efficiency (%) of king oyster mushroom

Sr. No.	Treatments	Total yield (g) per kg dry substrate	Biological efficiency (%)
1	T1- Sawdust	675.79	67.57
2	T2- Wheat straw	696.61	69.66
3	T3- Soybean straw	726.46	72.64
4	T4- Paddy straw	717.56	71.75
5	T5-Sugarcane bagasse	588.04	58.80
6	T6- Sugarcane trash	457.23	45.72
7	T7- Spent mushroom substrate	312.55	31.25
	SE±	20.73	2.07
	CD (0.05)	63.50	6.35

The findings are in line with those of Deora *et al.* (2021), who found that the biological efficiency of *Pleurotus eryngii* on rice straw and wheat straw was 88.4% and 76.7%, respectively.

According to Salame *et al.* (2021), the biological efficiency of *Pleurotus* spp. on wheat straw substrate ranged from 45.87% to 191.37%.

B) Fruiting of king oyster mushroom

Plate 2: Effect of different substrates on pinhead formation and yield performance of king oyster mushroom

Conclusion

It is concluded that the treatment T3 soybean straw took minimum days for spawn run (16.24 days) and pinhead formation after spawn run (11.44 days). The treatment T3 soybean straw required minimum days for 1st harvest (6.14 days), 2nd harvest (15.65 days) and 3rd harvest (23.79 days) after pinhead formation. The maximum pileus diameter was recorded in the treatment T3 soybean straw (6.72 cm). The maximum stipe length (7.82 cm) was recorded in treatment T1 sawdust substrate and the maximum stipe size (7.17 cm) was recorded in the treatment T3 soybean straw. The treatment T4 paddy straw had significantly highest average fruit body weight (30.18 g). It revealed that the treatment T3 soybean straw had highest number of fruits per kg dry substrate (24.87). Maximum yield 726.46 g/kg of substrate and also biological efficiency (72.64%) Thus, it could be concluded that the treatment T3 soybean straw was found to be superior in respect of growth and yield performance. It has given maximum yield of fresh mushroom i.e. 726.46 g per kg dry substrate.

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